

ACTIVITIES OF MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE FERGANA REGION

Abdukakharov Odiljon Alibek ugli

Researcher of Andizhan State University, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: In the article, during the years of independence, the activities of medical institutions in the Fergana region, the construction, repair and their equipment, the supply of hospitals with modern medical equipment, the importation of dental, physiotherapeutic, X-ray diagnostic devices developed in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, as well as their water, heating and sewage system, telephone communication system, electricity supply, autoclaves, drying cabinets, distiller, modern test-indicators, detergents and disinfectants were analyzed through primary sources.

Keywords: Fergana region, medical institutions, construction, repair, reconstruction, medical equipment.

In the early years of independence, a number of healthcare facilities were commissioned in the Fergana region, including polyclinics in the Kuva and Rishton districts, a 60-bed hospital in the Tashlak district, and dental clinics in the Kirguli and Baghdad districts. However, the construction of several important medical institutions remained incomplete due to the difficulties of the transitional period. These included a cardiology sanatorium in the Sokh district (the construction of which was later completed through privatization by entrepreneurs and currently provides high-quality medical services to the population), a maternity hospital in the Tashlak district, and a children's hospital in the city of Fergana.

Furthermore, the supply of medical institutions with equipment, essential instruments, medicines, and food products was inconsistent and inadequate. Most concerning, in the context of budget shortages, there were reported cases of misappropriation of funds allocated to the healthcare sector in the Uchkuprik and Baghdad districts, with resources being diverted to purposes unrelated to healthcare [2,22].

Within a three-year period, modern hospitals with a total capacity of 815 beds were commissioned in the region, along with outpatient clinics and polyclinics capable of receiving 324 patients, two sanitary-epidemiological stations, and a 160-bed home for infants and children.

In the city of Kokand, a 120-bed ophthalmology hospital and a polyclinic with a capacity of 200 patients were put into operation. Additionally, a 60-bed district hospital was established in the Tashlak district, and a 120-bed mother-and-child sanatorium was opened in the Besharik district.

In the city of Fergana, several specialized facilities were inaugurated, including a six-bed intensive care unit attached to the regional maternity hospital, a regional children's dental polyclinic equipped with 40 dental chairs, and a 200-bed regional children's hospital[3,27].

In order to ensure the timely provision of these institutions with modern medical equipment, 388 types of advanced medical devices – including dental, physiotherapeutic, X-ray diagnostic, and respiratory apparatus – were procured from medical equipment manufacturing plants of the Commonwealth of Independent States. These acquisitions, financed through the exchange of industrial raw materials and medical cotton, amounted to 1 billion 336 thousand coupon-sum and 316 thousand US dollars worth of imported medical equipment[4,29].

However, by 2000, the construction of medical facilities in the region had decreased twofold compared to 1998. It is particularly concerning that, of the 127 projects that had remained unfinished for many years in the region, 26 were healthcare institutions[1,364].

During this period, the total number of beds in 105 hospital institutions decreased by 325, reaching 15,609. The provision of hospital beds per 10,000 population amounted to 55.2. In the city of Kokand, this indicator stood at 77.6, significantly higher than the regional average. This can be explained by the retention of specialized beds intended to serve surrounding districts, given the city's role as a methodological center. In other districts and cities, the level of provision remained relatively uniform.

In particular, the scope of the work carried out is clearly evidenced by the allocation of 7.6 billion soums from the state budget – approximately one and a half times more than in the previous year – for the development of the material and technical base of healthcare institutions, as well as for equipping them with modern medical equipment, necessary fittings, and furniture. In addition, 7 billion soums were spent on capital repairs, financed through sponsorship funds[1,117].

As of January 1, 2009, 267 private treatment and preventive care institutions were registered in the region, bringing their total number to 719. As a result of systematic monitoring, notable improvements were achieved in the registration and accounting of individually operating non-governmental healthcare institutions.

In order to improve the sanitary and technical condition of treatment and preventive healthcare institutions, the central hospitals of the Rishon district and the medical association of the city of Kuvasay were fully renovated through capital repair works. In addition, the sterilization units of 19 city and district central hospitals were completely overhauled and reconstructed.

Furthermore, out of the non-state treatment and preventive care institutions that applied for licensing or re-registration, 99 facilities had their buildings brought up to required standards and were issued sanitary compliance certificates. In all of these institutions, sterilization units were established, and water heating systems such as “Ariston” and “Titan” devices were installed to ensure a continuous supply of hot water.

In the AIDS diagnostic laboratories of Uzbekistan district, Kuva and Rishon districts, and the inter-district center of Kokand city, both routine and major renovation works were fully completed. A total of 24 million 300 thousand soums was spent on these repair activities. In addition, capital renovation works worth 31 million 500 thousand soums were carried out at the AIDS diagnostic laboratory in the Besharik district[5].

In the region, reconstruction and renovation works were completed in 12 out of 22 maternity complexes under district medical associations. During this period, the healthcare system of the region comprised 78 hospitals with a total of 12,801 beds, 403 outpatient and polyclinic institutions with a single-shift reception capacity of 41,272 patients, 20 emergency medical service stations and units, 6 sanatoriums, 20 state sanitary-epidemiological surveillance centers, 2 children's homes, and 5 other medical institutions providing services to the population[6, 50].

During this period, the emergency medical service system was equipped with modern and improved transport facilities, including 13 “Hyundai-Ambulance” units and 39 “Damas-Ambulance” sanitary vehicles.

In order to further enhance the quality of emergency medical care, communication equipment was upgraded through the purchase of Motorola radio devices integrated with 8 stationary and 43 mobile telephone units, at a total cost of 50 million soums.

In implementation of the relevant resolution, estimates were prepared and approved by city and district administrations for the repair and improvement of the material and technical base of emergency medical service buildings and garages across the region, with a planned work volume of 711 thousand soums allocated for major and routine repairs.

During this period, a total of 276,544.0 soums worth of work was completed through sponsorship funds. In particular, 39,755.5 soums worth of construction and repair work was carried out using internal institutional resources. For the repair of existing vehicles, 21,300.0 soums were allocated from the material and technical development fund, while sponsors contributed 11,350.0 soums[7, 232].

During this period, a total of construction and repair works worth 663 million 740 thousand soums were carried out across the region for the reconstruction, capital repair, and routine maintenance of emergency medical service units.

Out of the planned 89 shelters and garages (boxes), 82 were newly constructed and completed, while 19 existing vehicle garages were fully renovated through major repair works[8, 96].

In conclusion, during the years of independence, a qualitatively new healthcare system was formed in the Fergana Valley, including the Fergana region, comprising a network of medical institutions that meet the highest standards and incorporate emergency medical care centers. In the regional center, multi-profile medical centers for adults and children were established, while in each district, rural medical posts equipped with modern medical devices and equipment began operating.

A robust system of modern healthcare institutions was created, including screening and perinatal centers, maternity hospitals, and wellness complexes, as well as rural medical posts, all of which were supplied with the necessary medical equipment and facilities.

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